

El Abayarde: Tego Calderón and the history, nationalism and negritude in Puerto Rico's Reggaeton

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1969146

IDV 402- Postcolonialism in the Caribbean: A negotiation between assimilation and dissociation

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Winter Semester 2023

Date of Submission: 12.01.2024

Index:

Introduction.....2

History of “Boricua” and Nationalism.....3

The emergence of Reggaeton and topics.....5

Black Skin White Mask.....9

El Abayarde.....13

Conclusions.....16

Bibliography.....17

*“Pero aunque mis canciones las cante un alemán
quiero que me entierren en el viejo San Juan”
-Residente, (René,2020)*

1.Introduction

It is in recent years that Reggaeton has taken the spotlight and has become one of the most famous, influential and listened music genres in the world.

Reggaeton as a music genre was created in the early 1990's where many artists from Puerto Rico transformed it into a worldwide phenomenon that is still nowadays one of the most listened to genres. From the old school generation of the late 1990's and early 2000's with legends like Daddy Yankee, Don Omar, Tego Calderón or Hector "*El Father*" to nowadays reggaeton main names like Bad Bunny, Anuel AA, J Balvin or Rauw Alejandro, we see that this phenomenon is worth researching as we see that, despite all the obscene lyrics and eccentric appearance, puerto rican reggaeton is a tool that has served as a mean to create a space for the negotiation of many topics that affect Puerto Rico's citizens being gun violence, sexuality, freedom, independence, racism, imperialism and slavery.

We will start our research by exploring the history of Puerto Rico and how it has transformed from an indigenous land habited by the "*Indios Tainos*" to an unclaimed territory that belongs to the United States.

Although Puerto Rico is a really diverse place, racism has always been present on the island as, despite most people being of mixed race, most of them see themselves as white and do not wish to be seen as black. Reggaeton in this matter has always been against this as many artists in the early 2000's were black and were proud of it as most of them dressed and shouted on their songs that they were proud to be black. Negritude as a social movement has helped afro-caribbean individuals to take pride in their african heritage. In this paper, we are going to define what a "race" is and the complexity of the term and we will look at how Cesaire and Fanon's ideas of Negritude helped shape not only Reggaeton but also other urban movements.

In this paper we will focus on the figure of one of the most recognized reggaeton artists in the history of the genre, Tego Calderon. Tego Calderon was born in Santurce, Puerto Rico although it was at an early age when he moved to Miami, United States, where he would come in contact with multiple cultures, which would influence his work. It was in 2002 when Tego Calderon released his most famous album and one of the best known in the history of Reggaeton, "El Abayarde" (2002). It is through the album "*El Abayarde*" that Tego Calderon portrays the nationalism, blackness and caribbeanness of Puerto Rico. Tego Calderon uses the negritude movement in his album to show that Puerto Ricans should take pride in their blackness and caribbeanness.

2. History of “Boricua” and Nationalism

Before the arrival of the Spaniards to the archipelago of Puerto Rico, this land already had a civilization that inhabited its lands, this nation is called the “*Taino*” Indians.

For the exploring of the history of Puerto Rico we will use Christian Millan text, “*Teaching Taíno: An Interrogation of Puerto Rican Indigenous Education*” (2021). This history of the Puerto Rican Indian tribe begins around 400 B.C., in the Orinoco Delta of Venezuela, where these tribes found their origin. The “*Taino*” indigenous tribes originated in Venezuela and, over hundreds of years, expanded throughout the Caribbean archipelago, coming to inhabit what is today considered Puerto Rico (Milian 2021: 16).

It was during the 15th and 16th centuries that the Spanish settlers discovered the island, proceeding to colonize it and, being the number of Taino settlers reduced in number since, many of the settlers began to reproduce with the indigenous women giving rise to the appearance of the so-called “*mestizos*” or “*criollos*”, a Spanish term that refers to Spanish citizens born in the American colonies.

With time, the Taino lineage will gradually disappear, with the number of indigenous people becoming smaller and smaller. Even so, in Puerto Rico, many inhabitants tend to consider themselves Tainos even though “(...), the Taíno went extinct in approximately the 16th century, the value of Taíno identification holds personal and political power” (Milian 2021: 17). The Taino legacy has left a mark on Puerto Rico’s history as, in the 20th century many members of independentist movements used their Taino legacy “as a way to claim a different national identity and ethnic homogeneity in direct opposition to the United States”(Milian 2021: 18).

In the year 1898, Puerto Rico became a colony of the United States of America after the Spanish-American war ended. It was in the year 1900, where the U.S congress, in order to establish control over the island passed the Foraker act, ending colonial rule in Puerto Rico (Power,2013:120). It was after this that Puerto Rico became attached to the United States as, “(...)in 1917 the U.S. Congress enacted the Jones Act, which made Puerto Ricans U.S. citizens.”(Power 2013: 120).It is the enactment of this act when Puerto Rico received the status of commonwealth, being supervised by the United States and its citizens considered as Americans.

It was during this the early 20th century that the first pro-independence movements began, it was the foundation of the PNP (Partido Nacionalista Puertorriqueño) in 1922 under the command of Albizu Campos, that the first pro-independent ideas started to take shape. The

PIP will become one of the main forces in the pro-independent ideology as, since the enactment of the Jones Act in 1917, the question of Puerto Rico's future has always been around as people still discuss whether they should join the United States or become an independent state. Puerto Rico is not an independent state and, therefore, its nationalist characteristics have been different from the rest of the Latin American countries as it is a country that is under the direct imperialistic rule of the United States (Maldonado 1976: 807). The nationalist movement in Puerto Rico was enacted by the upper classes and became a movement that was completely disconnected from the working classes as they were the main social group that was needed in order to establish a social order like it happened in Cuba. This disconnection from the working classes made the pro-independent movement to be classist as when it proposed the incorporation of the working class, the latter hesitated and rejected it (Maldonado 1976: 807). This classist actions by the bourgeois class created one of the main reasons for why Puerto Rico is still under the control of the United States as "The serious flaw of Puerto Rican nationalism has been, in our opinion, its inability to link itself to the great Puerto Rican working masses."(Maldonado 1976: 804).

It is, with time, that the sentiment of Puerto Rico as an independent nation has faded away as, the more they are tied to the United States, the more relationships they will have with its metropoli. The United States made sure to leave an impact on Puerto Rico as one of the main reasons for why Puerto Rico is still a commonwealth is that:

"The whole process by which the ties of cultural, ideological, economic, political and military dependence have been reinforced and has unquestionably contributed to cementing this force whose goal is the annexation of Puerto Rico to the United States as a state of the American union."(Maldonado 1976: 808)

Also many of the companies that are in Puerto Rico belong to owners that come from the United States and this very owners are the ones that stripe the power from the bourgeois Puerto rican classes as their lack of power and dependence on the US favors a pro-unification movement to the United States. The lack of power given to the working class has also been one of the reasons for Puerto Rico's national struggle as they are the only ones that can achieve a true solution for the social struggles of Puerto Rico. (Maldonado 1976:808).This lack of voice from the working class has created a certain amount of cultural products in order for them to be able to raise their voice when it comes to the national and identity issues of Puerto Rico. It is through culture that many Puerto Rican artists have talked about Puerto Rico's many identity and national problems and one of the movements that highlights Puerto Rican culture as something unique and has made them to be heard around the world is

Reggaeton. Reggaeton as a music genre that takes, in part, notions from rap as, both of them are genres that were born by the blending of different genres and that have served as a vessel for the underrepresented working classes to talk about the economic, identity and national, as Musician Davey D argues in Becky Blanchard article *The Social Significance of Rap & Hip-Hop Culture* (1999) "Keep in mind when brothas start flexing the verbal skillz, it always reflects what's going on politically, socially, and economical/y."(Blanchard 1999:1), therefore one of the reasons for the creation of reggaeton resembles this same statement.

3.The emergence of Reggaeton and topics

It is during the last two decades that Reggaeton has become the most popular music genre in the Spanish speaking countries and, during the last decade, more Reggaeton famous singers have experienced more visibility in the English speaking community. Reggaeton singers like Benito Martinez, better known as Bad Bunny, have increased their popularity as, in June 2020, Bad Bunny became the first artist to sing entirely in Spanish to feature on the cover of the Rolling Stone magazine (Solis 2020:1). This event seems impossible if we look at Reggaeton's history as nobody would have imagined that this genre that emerged in Panama during the 1990's would have experienced such rapid growth.

Before becoming one of the most listened genres worldwide and producing hit songs that broke music records like Luis Fonsi's *Despacito* (2017), Reggaeton was born during the 1990's in Panama but it was in Puerto Rico where this music genre was shaped and transformed into what it is today. Reggaeton appeared in Puerto Rico as a way for the subaltern classes of the marginalized low class Puerto Rican individuals to express themselves in different ways before becoming part of what Frankfurt School theorists Max Horkheimer and Theodor Adorno define as the "Culture Industry"(Solis 2020:1). Reggaeton opened up a space for the young Latino generations to negotiate topics like *latinidad*, nationalism identity, gender, sexuality, gun violence etc. (Solis 2020:1).

Reggaeton as a music genre started in the late 1980's with music productions in Panama which, in the early 1990's saw early manifestations of songs that resemble Reggaeton in Puerto Rico. Reggaeton takes inspiration from many other music genres such as Dancehall, Hip-Hop or Reggae. The name Reggaeton was given to this new genre by many artists and listeners as its early forms had a strong resemblance to the Jamaican music genre Reggae, even calling it "Spanish Reggae".(Marshall et al 2010:3)

Later on, Reggaeton increased its variety and took inspiration from other music genres like Calipso, Mambo, Salsa, Jibara Music while still maintaining Hip-Hop and Reggae influences

(Marshall et al 2010: 6) as, the genre we know today as Reggaeton is a really varied genre as it has influences and incorporates many traditional sounds from all the different countries that produce this type of music as, not only Reggaeton is produced in Puerto Rico, but also in countries like Spain, Argentina, Mexico, Colombia and many more Spanish speaking countries (Marshall et al 2010: 5).

As for nowadays modern style Reggaeton has left behind its ghetto aesthetics to adapt itself to a more pop style sound. Reggaeton lyrics that once were hypersexualized and violent lyrics that talked about violence, racism and had a nationalist Puerto Rican tone have been replaced with a more romantic approach that no longer approaches to the subaltern classes but rather has adapted to a more pop style and more familiar aesthetics as also its blending with the “trap” genre has gained popularity over the years with artists like Bad Bunny or Anuel AA. Despite its distancing from its racial lyrics there are still artists like Ozuna, who opens every song with the catchphrase “*el negrito de ojos claros*” meaning “the black men with light colored eyes”(Solis 2020:22).

Before Reggaeton became one of the most listened genres worldwide, it was a marginal genre that started to embody the true essence of the Caribbean youth as Reggaeton is a subaltern production made for the subaltern individuals (Solis 2020:42). Before its big crossover in 2004, Reggaeton was a genre born to talk about marginalized subaltern populations that lived in a continuous struggle surrounded by violence, sexism and racism in a “postcolonial” society that is dominated by the United States of America as, the genre of Reggaeton, was not only constructed with African and Caribbean music genres like Calipso or Reggae, but its ideological principles went against the Culture Industry as it embodied the subaltern traits of postcolonialism and blackness, going against the hegemonic values of whiteness, colonialism and occidentalism (Solis 2020:28).

As in terms of nationalism, Reggaeton in which most of its artists have made nationalist and independentist comments. One of the main examples of nationalist Puerto Rican artists is Rene Perez Joglar, better known for his rapper name “Residente”, who was the lead singer in the famous Puerto Rican group “Calle 13”. Residente is known for his support towards Puerto Rico’s independence as, in 2022, Residente released a song titled “This is not America”, in its song Residente makes a hard critique of the usage of the term “America” in order to refer to the United States as if they only existed, also it talks about colonialism and imperialism and calls out for a fight against imperialist oppression this can be seen on the first lines of the song where he says:

“Desde hace rato, cuando uste' llegaron; Ya estaban las huella' de nuestro' zapato'; Se robaron hasta la comida 'e gato; Y todavía se están lamiendo el plato” (Residente, This is Not America,2022)

There are multiple songs where Residente promotes anti-imperialist values and even refers to Puerto Rico as a country itself as, in his song, released in 2020 titled “Rene”, Residente where, at the end of verse 2, he refers to Puerto Rico as a country by saying “*Si la cagué, a mi paí' le dedico cuatro piso' de disculpa*”(Residente Rene,2020). Other topics that artists like Residente talk about is immigration as many Puerto Ricans live outside the island. It is in his song with his group Calle 13, “Pa'l norte” released in 2007, where they talk about the immigration and diaspora of latin american and its position that ties with the global subalternity (Solis 2020:42) as they say “*Ser un emigrante, ese es mi deporte, hoy me voy pa'l norte sin pasaporte (...) vamos por debajo de la tierra como las ardillas*”(Pa'l Norte,Calle 13,2007)(Solis 2020:42).

Apart from racial and nationalist topics, (racism and negritude topics will be discussed later), Reggaeton faced numerous critics for its vulgar and inappropriate treatment of homosexuality and women as its hypersexualized lyrics and the so-called “*perreo*” are trends that are, according to some critics, harmful towards the views of women as, not only this issue harms the genre, but also the direct relation that artists have created when relating marginality establishes with criminality is considered as something that harms the hegemonic center (Solis 2020:35,36). My critique of this claims relies on the foundation that Reggaeton is a genre made by the subaltern and that uses what is “not civilized” to go against the traditional values by using the tainted moral values as using them causes the same effect that west beliefs caused centuries ago by imposing to their beliefs therefore creating a counter culture by using this “tainted forms”. As Naya Rivera argues on her publication “*Hate it or love it: Global crossover of reggaeton music in the digital age*”(2014), is that to engage with these tainted musical genres is to open yourself to moral corruption and to destroy the discursive fabric of the chaste, enlightened and the civilized national body and constructed socially non-africanized big family (Rivera 2014:89). Therefore we can state that Reggaeton uses countercultures and uses the “dark” aspects of society to portray true reality.

When it comes to female violence, Reggaeton has done a good job when helping to empower women as in Puerto Rican society the mistreatment of women and “*machismo*” have been issues that have troubled Puerto Rican society for centuries. Many women in Puerto Rican society struggle with their gender condition as their subjugation by males makes them to be targeted by being called “*sluts*” Marysol W. Asencio discusses this term on her publication

Machos and Sluts: Gender, Sexuality, and Violence among a Cohort of Puerto Rican Adolescents (1999) where she defines the term that many Puerto Rican women faced to be called:

“(…)(1) an inability to love, (2) an inability to settle down, (3) an abnormal sex drive, (4) non discrimination among sexual partners, (5) carelessness, (6) the capacity for other unacceptable behaviors such as infidelity and lying, and (7) lack of respect for one's own body and self and, therefore, inability to claim respect from others(…)”
(Asencio 1999:113)

The “slut” women therefore are viewed as dehumanized and not deserving of respect as it is believed that they need to be punished and, therefore violent conducts must be used around them. Another aspect that women suffer in Puerto Rico is the lack, not only of respect among their male partners but also the hardships of not being able to receive an education and being forced to take care of the house (Solis 2020:35). Many artists like Ivy Queen talked about this issues as in her song “Como Mujer” (1996), Ivy Queen discusses the struggle of Puerto Rican women and youth to be able to get education or a job and their lack of opportunities in the country as she says:

“*Soy blanco de la policía y de la injusticia, ser confinada sin tener malicia (...) Te sacan de la escuela sin haber terminado para criar a tus propios hermanos(...) Y tu madre se divorció. Hogar de llanto y también de dolor*” (Ivy Queen, Como Mujer, 1996)(Solis 2020:35)

In conclusion, Reggaeton is a blending of different caribbean genres that uses subaltern culture to address the subaltern individuals and defy the traditional western culture that has been imposed to them denouncing all the hardships and social struggles they go against as, issues of identity gender, nationalism, immigration or feminism are being negotiated and discussed. Another important issue that it must be addressed is the problem of race as, despite the caribbean being a really diverse region, it is the traditional racial beliefs of the west that have implanted race discriminative ideologies in Puerto Rican society and, movements like the Negritude have helped to defy them as in the next chapter we will discuss the work of DuBois, Fanon and Cesaire and discuss the impact on Negritude in Puerto Rico and Reggaeton following also the legacy and work of Reggaeton artist, Tego Calderon and his debut album “*El Abayarde*”(2002).

4.Black Skin, White Mask

To first understand how racism in Reggaeton works, we must first understand how the concept of “race” is understood in the caribbean. Firstly, we must highlight that the concept of “race” does not exist as, there is no biological reason or proof that can show as a “race”, it was american sociologist, W.E.B Du Bois that, in the late 19th century, provided us with a different definition of “race” as, in his book, *The Conservation of Races* (1897), Du Bois argued that race was a vast family of human beings that shared common knowledge language, history and traditions that shared the same goals and ideals of life (DuBois, 1897:190). This definition given by DuBois broke the biological preconceptions of race by arguing that it was based on social and geographical factors and not on biological ones.

The caribbean as a region is very diverse as many migration waves caused it to be a very diverse region and Puerto Rico is no exception as the “(...)contemporary Puerto Rican person, is that she is a mixture of three ancestral “races”: Indigenous, European (Spanish), and African”(Llorens et al 2017: 155) but this does not indicate that racism does not exist in Puerto Rico. Although the Caribbean is a diverse region and many of its inhabitants descend from different locations, racism towards dark skinned individuals is a matter of social concern. When asked about their race, most Puerto Ricans will rather choose to be identified as white as:

“The first tendency (choosing White) is best illustrated by the 2000 and 2010 census results for Puerto Rico, where an overwhelming majority, 80.5 percent of Puerto Ricans (in 2000), and 74 percent (in 2010), self-identified as “White” only in the census.”(Llorens et al 2017: 156)

This tendency of Puerto Ricans choosing to be “white” is believed by scholars as a phenomenon that happens because of the awareness that Puerto Ricans have of the privileges that a “white” racial status gives in the eyes of the U.S authorities on the island (Llorens et al 2017: 157). Therefore, we can conclude that this fear of being labeled as “black” in Puerto Rico derives from a fear of punishment of the metropoli as, despite the caribbean region being really diverse, it is the metropolis racial customs and beliefs that interfere with Puerto Rico’s racial ideas therefore creating a sense of “black” rejection, not because of the color or traditions, but of what it means to the metropolis authorities as, when asking dark skinned Puerto Ricans on if they had ever experienced racism, it was reported that many of them were more likely to describe or report racist experiences in their daily lives (Llorens et al 2017: 165).

In the study we have been referring to previous times, conducted by Hilda Llorens, Carlos G. García-Quijano and Isar P. Godreau, called “*Racismo en Puerto Rico: Surveying Perceptions of Racism*” (2017), it was found that over 71 percent of Puerto Ricans that self described as black had experienced major racist experiences being most of them at their jobs and on the streets (Llorens et al 2017: 165). Therefore, we can conclude that, despite being a really diverse region with people that have European, African and indigenous heritage, Puerto Rico is a country that suffers from racism towards their dark skinned citizens. This racism is different as it does not come from a core belief in the country's culture that provokes a hate towards black individuals but rather an external belief that has been inserted due to the cultural and political influence that the United States exercises over Puerto Rico.

It is during the last decades of the twentieth century that many cultural and political movements came to defy the beliefs that black individuals were inferior to white individuals. Social movements like the “Negritude” movement (meaning blackness), who were previously formed at the beginning of the twentieth century, have helped to shape these urban movements. It was during the late nineteenth century that two important African scholars who, at the time, were two of the most influential black men in the United States, Booker T. Washington and the previously mentioned W.E.B. Du Bois, had differences on their views of the future situation of African Americans. It was in his book, *The Souls of the Black Folk* (1903) where Du Bois addressed Washington's ideas and criticized him for his views as he argued that his ideas were transforming the African Americans into second class citizens as he said that his ideas had disfranchised the African Americans, caused a second civil rights status of inferiority for them and withdraw them of the aid of any high institution for the training and education of them (DuBois 1903:30). DuBois accused Washington of prioritizing political power over civil rights as he thought that gaining civil rights for African Americans and to be considered as fully equal to the whites was more important. DuBois also advocated for the separation of both Whites and Blacks as he did not believe that these two cultures could co-exist together as he said on his book, *The Conservation of Races* (1897):

“For the accomplishments of these ends we need race organizations: Negro colleges, Negro newspapers, Negro business organizations, a Negro school of literature and art, and an intellectual clearing house, for all these products of the Negro mind, which we may call a Negro Academy” (DuBois 1897: 196)

It was DuBois ideas of a separated black culture that won the intellectual battle against Booker T. Washington as DuBois went on to inspire the future civil rights movement. Furthermore DuBois founded and directed the NAACP (The National Association for the

Advancement of Colored People) and inspired many cultural and political movements like the Harlem Renaissance, Negritude or the previously named, “Civil Rights Movement”. DuBois on a black culture inspired many black artists to create music of their own as many music genres like Jazz, Rock or Hip-Hop were born out of these ideas. During this time, movements like the Negritude emerged to discuss blackness and caribeaness as many french speaking authors, like Martinique's native scholar, Aime Cesaire, lead this movement as they reflected on the colonial situation and the future of blackness. It was his publication, “*Discours sur le Colonialisme*” (1950), that acted as a direct attack to colonialism and critiqued the west and the situation of black individuals. It was undeniable that the black skinned individual not only felt rejected from society but, they viewed themselves as disposable agents in a white oriented society that had been fabricated for the whites and that had forcibly incorporated them making them feel oppressed and unable to be themselves as, Abiola Irele argues on her publication “*Negritude-Literature and Ideology*”(1965):

“The overwhelming sentiment that dominates in this connection is the black man's sense of separation from his own world and of being thrown into a social system with whose cultural values he can strike no personal relation”(Irele 1965: 500)

It was the movement of the negritude that emerged as a counter culture to the hegemonic values of slavery and black inferiority and looked for the emancipation of the values of slavery subjugation and independence from the alienation of the whites through manifestations and revolts (Irele 1965:499) as the black man had been historically used as an economic tool by the west and, as Cesaire recalled, they had been reduced to a mere object (Irele 1965: 500). When discussing the relationship that movements like the Negritude have with urban caribbean movements like Reggaeton we need to explore the ideas and work of one of Cesaire pupils, french-martinique philosopher and scholar, Franz Fanon. It was Frantz Fanon's book “*Black Skin, White Mask*” (1952) that sets the racial background and relates the Negritude movement with urban musical movements like Reggaeton. In her publication, “*Frantz Fanon and the Negritude Movement How Strategic Essentialism Subverts Manichean*”(2013), author Cynthia R. Nielsen argues that “In other words, Fanon that the colonized person in some sense actively participates in and thus of her white-scripted history” (Nielsen 2013:342) this passive participation by the black skinned individuals states that the black individual is not recognized as a person, but rather has become dehumanized, as not only he has internalized their inferiority but also endured extreme psychological pressures by the dominant hegemonic society that they have lost their sense of identity (Nielsen 2013: 342).

Both Fanon and Césaire recognized that the black Caribbean individual had lost his sense of belonging and cultural identity due to its colonial past, slavery and oppression of their cultures, as whites had labeled the black as being evil, inferior and subhuman and, not only they labeled it but made black individuals to believe this fallacy. Both Césaire and Fanon argued that in order for the Afro-Caribbean individual to be free, it was necessary to deconstruct white narratives and to favor and recapture blackness and transform it into something positive (Nielsen 2013:345). As Césaire argued in his famous *Discourse et Colonialisme* (1950) that:

“we asserted that our Negro heritage was worthy of respect, and that this heritage was not relegated to the past, that its values were values that could still make an important contribution to the world.” (Césaire 1950: 92)

Although Fanon was Césaire’s pupil and had respect for him, both scholars had their differences as Fanon critiqued his work on various occasions. Fanon’s more radical approach towards Pan-African change clashed with multiple scholars as he believed that in order to achieve true independence, social change through political structures had to be sought (Nielsen 2013:348). Fanon’s radical views helped to the creation of cultural urban movements that helped deconstruct and enhance black culture and black pride as they were not only cultural movements but also political and social movements that talked about the struggles and political ideas of the working oppressed classes. This is the case of Puerto Rico’s Reggaeton as many artists through their songs have addressed the racial problem in Puerto Rico by identifying themselves as black in their songs, something that people in Puerto Rico do not do.

One of the main problems, when it comes to Puerto Rico’s racial problem is the lack of officiality it receives as it is an aggravation factor (Llorens et al 2017:175) that not only minimizes the struggle of Puerto Rican black citizens but also promotes racial discrimination because of “*mestizo*” citizens’ tendencies to label themselves as white and therefore rejecting their own blackness. But it is the movement of Reggaeton that we have seen many artists label themselves as black and this has served as an official acknowledgment to the problem as Llorens, Quijano and Gordeau argue:

“Such commitment and acknowledgement—as supported by this and future research—would help advance the anti-racism cause in Puerto Rico and give credence to the problem of racism as a real social ill rather than one that is made up and felt only by a few disgruntled members of society.” (Llorens et al 2017: 175)

It is the work and social relevance of Reggaeton artists like Tego Calderon that have helped to raise awareness about the racial problem in Puerto Rico as many of Tego Calderon's songs not only show pride in being Puerto Rican and Caribbean but also display Black pride to its highest levels as he is considered to be, not only one of the pioneers of the Reggaeton movement, but also a figure that has helped make Puerto Ricans to be proud of their ancestry and blackness.

It is in his debut album, "El Abayarde" (2002) that Tego Calderon combines different Caribbean music genres and uses Reggaeton as a tool to show pride in being Caribbean, Black and Puerto Rican and also goes against the western tradition by using the "tainted" traditions of the Caribbean and the indigenous people..

5. El Abayarde

Considered by many as one of the pioneers of the Reggaeton movement, Tegu Calderón Rosario, better known by his nickname "Tego Calderón", is a Puerto Rican actor, rapper and songwriter that was born in Santurce, Puerto Rico. It is alongside with rapper Don Omar that, both Tego and Don Omar are considered two of the biggest Reggaeton legends that have ever existed as they both have been pioneers and have inspired many future generations of Reggaeton artists.

In their book "*La Verdad: An International Dialogue on Hip Hop Latinidades*" (2016), authors Melissa Castillo-Garsow and Jason Nichols discuss on chapter 5, written by Jason Nichols, the influence that both Don Omar and Tego Calderon have had in representing spiritual and black identity in Puerto Rico as also for their national identity. As we previously discussed, Reggaeton was created in Panama but it has become part of Puerto Rico's true essence as we have seen throughout this paper how much it has shaped the Latino community in the 30 years of its existence.

As Castillo and Nichols argue, "Any story about Puerto Rican music invariably begins with the story of the Puerto Rican people." (Castillo, Nichols 2016:81), so therefore we can see that much of the topics discussed on the negotiation of space that Reggaeton opens up are topics that represent Puerto Rico's history, identity and society and, both Don Omar and Tego Calderón use this space of negotiation to represent not only the country's struggle and national identity but also they use the Negritude movement by identifying as Black individuals as "Two of Reggaeton's biggest stars have overtly chosen identity that is Black." (Castillo, Nichols 2016:86).

This choice by both Tego Calderon and Don Omar has had a significant impact in Puerto Rico's social landscape because, before they made this choice many *mestizos* in Puerto Rico decided to identify themselves as whites but, by two of the biggest Reggaeton stars in the world identifying as black, this has had an impact as nowadays more modern Reggaeton artists like Ozuna. Ozuna is known for opening his songs with the phrase "*El negrito de ojos claros*", this catchphrase not only identifies him as black, but highlights his pride in being black differentiating him from his peers (Solis 2020:22) and it is this pride shown by Puerto Rico's younger generation on their blackness that prove both Tego and Don Omar's work as it is "Both Don Omar and Tego Calderon personify the spiritual Blackness of reggaeton and ultimately of the Puerto Rican culture"(Castillo,Nichols 2016:88).

To show how both of them embody this culture we are going to focus on the discography of Tego Calderon as he possesses the album we are going to analyze which is called, "*El Abayarde*"(2002) which is Tego Calderon's debut album. For this analysis we are going to use Rolling Stone's article on the 20th anniversary of the album and also we will use the famous interview that Tego Calderon did in NPR in 2008

"El Abayarde", as we previously mentioned, is Tego Calderon's debut album and is considered to be one of the first albums that truly embodied the true characteristics of Reggaeton as it was released in a time where, alongside Tego, many other artists were also releasing their albums, artists like Don Omar or Daddy Yankee, who at the time released his famous song "*Gasolina*".

The album possesses a very peculiar name "*Abayarde*", this word means "*hormiga*" in Spanish or "ant" in English, which is an insect that when it bites, it itches. This reference to an ant that itches makes allusion to how reggaeton is supposed to be and how it is supposed to be made. As we previously mentioned reggaeton was made by the subaltern for the subaltern and therefore this subaltern people (the ants) they revolt and bite by creating this counterculture and, by having gotten so famous it has caused the western world to get "itching" from this "biting". In conclusion the name itself is a reference to him as he sees himself as an ant that is using all his power to go against the postcolonial conceptions and fight racism and imperialism.

When it comes to the beats of the songs we can appreciate that the album is composed of a great variety of instruments and of musical genres. Tego, as Reggaeton does, gains inspiration from other movements like Hip-Hop, Reggae or Jazz as in most of the songs of the albums influences and the beats of the songs gain inspiration from them. One of the most interesting aspects of the album's music is the usage of the "*barriles*", this instrument was used during

the slavery times in Puerto Rico, “*barriles*”, which translates to barrel in English, where a set of drums made out of rum barrels used during slavery to produce music.

The album starts with an interlude in which the arrival of “*El Abayarde*” is announced, which means that this person is like an ant as, although it is small in power its bite is really powerful and stands against oppression.

When the interlude finishes, it passes on to the first song of the album titled “*Abayarde*” which marks the arrival of Tego. In this song, Tego shows his black pride and national pride as in the song he says “*Me inculcaron semillita de esta cultura/Desde la cuna, agradecido de esta negrura*” which means that since birth this culture was taught to him and that he is proud and thankful of his blackness. This phrase not only shows the relation of Reggaeton with negritude and the black pride that Tego embodies, but it alludes to his family as his family were afro-latin Puerto Ricans that not only were pro independence but also proudly black. Tego’s pride for Puerto Rico is also shown in this songs as in one verse he says “*Boricua hasta el hueso*” meaning “*boricua*” (popular term that is used to call Puerto Ricans) to the bones, which also highlights the nationalist pride of Tego.

It is after the first interlude that also says “*Llego Tego Calderon*” alongside with the “*barriles*” that we mentioned before. This song titled “*Loiza*” alludes to a district in San Juan, Puerto Rico. In this song, Tego uses rap and afro-caribbean music to produce a rebellious and political song that calls for equality between blacks and whites. In this song, Tego calls out the myth of racial equality in Puerto Rico that, as we mentioned in previous chapters, in spite of being a really diverse region, racism against the black individuals in Puerto Rico is a big issue that lacks true recognition and is not sufficiently addressed as in the song lyrics Tego says “*Me quieren hacer pensar que soy parte de una trilogía racial, donde to el mundo es igual sin especial*” calling out for the racial bias. He also in other lines like “*Cambiaron las cadenas por esposas*” and “*Mi pueblo negro no padece, Porque tu crees que se lo merece*” he highlights that nothing has changed and that he does not understand why there is still such racist tendencies amongst Puerto Ricans. Regardless of this Tego still shows pride in being black as he says “*Yo soy niche orgulloso de mis raíces*”, showing also pride in being African, Caribbean and Puerto Rican.

In other songs, like “*Pa’ que retozen*” or “*Al Natural*”, Tego also discusses other issues like violence, women and language. In this song he goes against the system as he alters the significance of the word “*retozen*” which means “to run or jump” and alters it to describe the experience that the subaltern has when facing unpredictable events.

When it comes to violence, Tego calls out for liberation from it as he portrays in a way that shows how people need to be freed with lines like “*Maldita maldad que destruye la humanidad*” which means, "damn evil that destroys humanity". Finally, the beats and allusion to women dancing calls out for the previously mentioned subaltern characteristic of reggaeton as it tries to empower women to dance and portray themselves in a way that is viewed as un-pure or dirty by the western society. In conclusion, we can agree that “El Abayarde” is an album that represents a loud, powerful black individual that shows pride in his caribbean and african roots and that is not afraid of fighting the oppression of the western world.

6. Conclusions

As a movement Reggaeton has changed, it is now more pop driven but, we cannot deny the fact that it once was a socially driven movement that went against the notion of the western culture. Reggaeton is a music genre that was built and created through the influence and incorporation of many musical genres that were also created for the same purpose that reggaeton was built for as, this genre was created by the subaltern and it is for the subaltern to identify it. As Nichols and Castillo argued “Any story about Puerto Rican music invariably begins with the story of the Puerto Rican people.” (Castillo, Nichols 2016:81) and we have seen how artists like Tego Calderon take pride in their African and indigenous heritage to tell the story of their country by discussing the social issues of the Puerto Rican people as, although it was created in Panama, it is undeniable that Puerto Ricans have perfected and molded this genre into something that truly embodies the cultural heritage and traditions of the afro-hispanic caribbean cultures.

We have seen that Reggaeton, through its grotesque and exotic rhythms, deals with problems like racism as we have verified its connection to the Negritude movement as it is a music genre that shows pride in being dark skinned as many black Puerto Ricans like Don Omar, Tego Calderón or Ozuna have shown pride and claim their black heritage in a country where most *mestizos* are afraid to be considered as such. To answer our research question, Is Reggaeton more than its lyrics, does it take part in social movements or is it just a grotesque genre? Yes, it is more than its lyrics as nowadays, it might have drifted away from its roots but, Reggaeton has become a musical space of negotiation for the subaltern masses to understand each other by defying the western cultures that call their ways as “tainted” or “unpure”. Reggaeton is a musical movement that claims blackness, caribbeaness and gives a sense of belonging and identity to not only the Puerto Ricans, but also the latino community and its members of the diaspora.

7. Bibliography MLA (with albums and songs)

Asencio, Marysol W. "Machos and Sluts: Gender, Sexuality, and Violence among a Cohort of Puerto Rican Adolescents." *Division of Sociomedical Sciences Columbia University School of Public Health*, vol. 13, 1999, pp. 107-126, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10322604/>.

Blanchard, Becky. "The Social Significance of Rap & Hip-Hop Culture." *Ethics of Development in a Global Environment (EDGE)*, 1999, pp. 1-10, https://hiphoparchive.org/sites/default/files/the_social_significance_of_rap_hip_hop_culture.pdf.

Calderon, Tego. "El Abayarde". BMG Distribution, White Lion Records, 2003.

Calle 13. "Pa'l Norte (feat. Orishas)". *Residente o Visitante*, 5020 Records, 2007. Spotify <https://open.spotify.com/track/03O9Ag8SXuCzNLajTet4NM?si=f268ad852d3c4d3e>

Depestre, René, et al. "AN INTERVIEW WITH AIMÉ CÉSAIRE." *Discourse on Colonialism*, NYU Press, 2000, pp. 79–94. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt9qfkrm.5>. Accessed 31 Dec. 2023.

Du Bois, W. E. B. "'The Conservation of Races (1897)'. Nations and Identities: Classic Readings." *Oxford*, 2001, pp. 190-199.

DuBois, W. E. B. "The Souls of Black Folk." *The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 2009, <https://www.jpnafrican.org/ebooks/3.4eBookSoulofBlackFolk.pdf>.

Irele, Abiola. "Negritude-Literature and Ideology." *The Journal of Modern African Studies*, vol. 3, no. 4, 1965, pp. 499-526, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/159175>.

Ivy Queen. "Como Mujer". *En mi Imperio*, Ivy Queen Musa Sound Corp, 1997. Spotify <https://open.spotify.com/track/7G96e9UnlxQTG4Xpp0K1dj?si=be1006926460489a>

Lloréns, Hilda, Carlos G. García-Quijano, and Isar P. Godreau. "Racismo en Puerto Rico: Surveying Perceptions of Racism." *Centro Journal*, vol. 29, no. 3, 2017, pp. 154-183, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323277955_Racismo_en_Puerto_Rico_Surveying_perceptions_of_racism.

Maldonado Denis, Julio. "Las Perspectivas del Nacionalismo Latinoamericano: El caso de Puerto Rico." *Revista Mexicana de Sociología*, vol. 38, no. 4, 1976, pp. 799-810, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3539709?origin=crossref>.

Milian, Christian. "Teaching Taíno: An Interrogation of Puerto Rican Indigenous Education." *Yale College Education Studies Program*, 2021, https://educationstudies.yale.edu/sites/default/files/files/Christian_Milian_FinalCapstone.pdf.

Nichols, Jason, and Melissa Castillo-Garsow. *LA VERDAD An International Dialogue on Hip Hop Latinidades*. Ohio State University, 2016, pp. 80-88 <https://kb.osu.edu/items/7a6aea09-8aea>

Nielsen, Cynthia R. "FRANTZ FANON AND THE NÉGRITUDE MOVEMENT: How Strategic Essentialism Subverts Manichean Binaries." *The Johns Hopkins University Press*, vol. 36, no. 2, 2013, pp. 342-152, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/24264913>.

Power, Margaret. "Nationalism in a Colonized Nation: The Nationalist Party and Puerto Rico Nacionalismo en una Nación Colonizada: El Partido Nacionalista y Puerto Rico." *Revista digital de Historia y Arqueología desde el Caribe colombiano*, vol. 20, 2013, pp. 119-137, <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=4653890>.

Residente. "This Is Not America (feat.Iyebi)". *This Is Not America*, Sony Music Entertainment US Latin LLC, 2022. Spotify <https://open.spotify.com/track/7d8LusdMBU3yWUSWBpETjG?si=417788faa154419a>

Residente. "René". *René*, Sony Music Entertainment US Latin LLC, 2020. Spotify <https://open.spotify.com/track/6gm12xlADJwiBbHIKBXzGW?si=dbbd35de2723466e>

Rivera, Michelle. "HATE IT OR LOVE IT: GLOBAL CROSSOVER OF REGGAETÓN MUSIC IN THE DIGITAL AGE." *College of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*, 2014, <http://hdl.handle.net/2142/49834>.

Solis, Regina. "Aquí nos encontramos, ahí nos imaginan: el reggaetón como espacio de negociación identitaria." *University of Sheffield*, 2020, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348393342_Aqui_nos_encontramos_ahi_nos_imaginan_el_reggaeton_como_espacio_de_negociacion_identitaria, doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.30759.98726.

STONE, ROLLING. "20 años después, El Abayarde de Tego Calderón todavía posee el crudo y poderoso espíritu del reggaetón.", 2022. <https://es.rollingstone.com/20-anos-despues-el-abayarde-de-tego-calderon-todavia-posee-el-crudo-y-poderoso-espiritu-del-reggaeton/>

Wayne, Marshall, Z. Rivera Raquel, and Deborah P. Hernandez. "Los circuitos socio-sónicos del reggaetón." *Trans. Revista Transcultural de Música*, vol. 14, 2010, pp. 1-9, <https://www.redalyc.org/pdf/822/82220947017.pdf>.